

Original Research

A convenient synthesis, anticonvulsant screening and neurotoxicity study of novel quinoline incorporated thiazolidin-4-one derivatives as potential anticonvulsant agents

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Received: July 10, 2021/ Accepted: August 19, 2021/
Published online: 20 August 19, 2021

Abstract: Epilepsy is a neurological disorder involving a local body to the whole body part. The disease is not fatal, but the consequences are very grave. There is no final and permanent cure for the disease. Moreover, drug-resistant epilepsies are evolving, making the healthcare give a limited space to treat the disease. Therefore, new drug molecules are continuously needed to treat drug-resistant epilepsies. Herein, the authors report the synthesis and antiepileptic screening of a series of quinoline-incorporated thiazolidin-4-ones. The synthesized compounds were characterized and subjected to maximal electroshock seizure (MES) and subcutaneous pentylenetetrazol (*sc*PTZ)-induced seizure tests. Neurotoxicity was evaluated via rotarod and ethanol potentiation tests. Among the compounds tested, **19c**, **20b**, **20c**, **21b** and **21f** showed maximum protection against MES test model. In *sc*PTZ test, compounds **20c**, **20d**, **21b** and **21f** showed maximum activity. In rotarod and ethanol potentiation tests only one compound that is **21b** showed neuromotor toxicity. More research is needed to validate the safety and efficacy of these compounds.

Keywords: Anticonvulsants; Hepatotoxicity; Neurotoxicity; Quinoline; Thiazolidin-4-one

1. Introduction

Epilepsy is a neurological disorder caused by an excessive discharge of neurotransmitters that occurs suddenly, uncontrollably, and without warning. It's one of the most common neurological conditions, affecting a substantial percentage of the population (1). Although the specific cause of epilepsy is unknown, factors linked to the disorder include brain trauma, strokes, brain cancer, and drug and alcohol abuse, among others. Some types of epilepsy have recently been connected to the passing of specific genes from one generation to the next (2). The disease's multifaceted nature causes a significant degree of impediment to the successful development of antiepileptic medicines (3). Approximately 20–30% of epileptic individuals are resistant to practically all antiepileptic medications now available in clinical settings. There is dose-related toxicity and idiosyncratic side effects in all currently licenced AEDs (4). The hunt for innovative, highly potent, and more selective agents with fewer adverse effects is still underway. There were previously sufficient data indicating that nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds (5–7) exhibited promising antiepileptic efficacy. Quinoline derivatives have long been recognised as a promising pharmacophore, although few analogues have been developed and investigated for anticonvulsant efficacy. Different heterocyclic moieties were coupled to the quinoline pharmacophore, resulting in a considerable increase in anticonvulsant efficacy (8, 9).

Ralitoline, (N-(2-chloro-6-methylphenyl)-2-(3-methyl-4-oxo-1, 3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene) acetamide) which contains a thiazolidinone ring system is chemically distinct from other antiepileptic drugs (Figure 1). This drug possesses remarkable anticonvulsant properties, as demonstrated in various animal models of antiepileptic tests. The efficacy of this chemical appears to be

equivalent to, if not superior to, that of standard antiepileptic medications (10).

Figure 1: Structural comparison between ralitoline and the title compounds

The half-life of ralitoline was found to be short due to the fact that it is hydrolyzed because of its amide bond (11). Until now, the progress in the structure optimization of ralitoline was not systematically made and a very few literatures documented different physico-chemical parameters of this drug. Piecing all the information together, we developed an idea for the structure modification of thiazolidinone pharmacophore by attaching with several quinoline derivatives. The probable synergistic effect was expected as both pharmacophores are well documented in controlling seizures of many types.

Figure 2: 3D overlapping of title compounds with ralitoline

The single covalent bonds between the quinoline and thiazolidinone rings restrict hydrolytic cleavage (in contrast to ralitoline which hydrolyzes fast) of the title compounds. When title compounds were overlapped

with the ralitoline, a good superimposition was observed indicating the title compounds blocking ability with sodium channel (Figure 2). Furthermore, the derivatives are fulfilling all the basic requirements needed for a compound to elicit anticonvulsant activity (12). The essential structural features that could be responsible for an interaction with the active site of voltage-gated sodium channels were a hydrophobic HP unit (R), an electron donor (D) group and a hydrogen donor/acceptor (HBD) unit (Figure 3). Therefore, the present work is expected to produce some ideal compounds which may further be optimized and investigated to generate some drug candidates.

Title compounds

Figure 3: Essential structural features that could be responsible for an interaction with the active site of voltage-gated sodium channels; hydrophobic unit-R, an electron donor-D, hydrogen donor/acceptor-HBD unit.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemistry

Melting points were determined by the open capillary method with electrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded as KBr (pallet) on Bio Rad FT-IR spectrophotometer and ¹H and ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded on Bruker DPX 400 MHz spectrophotometer using DMSO-*d*₆ or CDCl₃ as a NMR solvent. TMS used as an internal standard and chemical shift data are reported in parts per million (in ppm) where s, bs, d, t and m designated as singlet, broad singlet, doublet, triplet and multiplet, respectively. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL SX102 / DA-6000 mass spectrometer using *m*-nitrobenzylalcohol as a matrix and elemental analysis on Vario-EL III CHNOS-Elementar analyzer. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was

performed to monitor the progress of the reaction and purity of the compounds, spot being located under iodine vapour or UV-light.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of the title compounds (19a-19f, 20a-20f, 21a-21f)

Reagents and conditions: (i) acetic acid:acetic anhydride (Ac₂:AcOH, equal volumes, reflux; (ii) N,N-Dimethylformamide, phosphoryl chloride; (iii) hydroxylamine hydrochloride, sodium formate in formic acid (iv) sodium hydrosulfide (NaSH), MgCl₂·6H₂O/DMF(v) chloroacetic acid/sod. acetate-ethanol (vi) secondary amines (N(R₁R₂)/HCl/ paraformaldehyde / ethanol

2.1.1. Synthesis of substituted N-aryl acetamide [compounds (4-6)]

To a mixture of acetic acid–acetic anhydride (Ac₂: AcOH, equal volumes) 20 ml, substituted anilines (0.1 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for specified time. The contents of the flask were cooled and poured on the ice water with constant stirring. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from aqueous ethanol to give a white to creamy white crystalline solid.

2.1.2. Synthesis of 2-Chloro-8-substitutedquinoline-3-carboxaldehyde [compounds (7-9)]

N,N- Dimethylformamide (0.125 mol, 9.13 gm) was cooled to 0°C in flask equipped with a drying tube and phosphoryl chloride (0.35 mol, 57.3 gm) was added

dropwise with stirring. To this solution was added appropriately substituted N-arylacetamide (0.05 mol) and after 5 minutes the solution was heated under reflux for specified time at 75°C. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice-water (300ml) and stirred for 30 minutes at 0-10°C. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with cold water, dried, and recrystallised from ethylacetate as light yellow shiny needle shaped crystals. The solid obtained tested positive with Schiff's test. The purity of compound was checked by TLC using TEF (5:4:1) as mobile phase.

2.1.3. Synthesis of substitutedquinoline-3-carbonitrile

[compounds (10-12)]

To a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.515 mol) and sodium formate (0.687 mol) in formic acid (anhydrous, 300 mL), substitutedquinoline-3-carbaldehyde (0.343 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was heated to a temperature of about 100°C for about 8 hours. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to about 40°C and water was added to it. The reaction mixture was cooled to about 25°C and stirred for about 1 hour. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. The solid was then dissolved in acetone at about 50°C and water was added slowly over a period of about 30 minutes. The mixture was cooled to about 25°C and again stirred for about 1 hour. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with acetone: water (1:1) mixture and dried to obtain the title product.

2.1.4. Synthesis of quinoline-2-carbothioamide [compounds (13-15)]

To a suspension of sodium hydrosulfide (NaSH) (hydrate, 70 % w/w) (11.98 g, 0.150 mol) and MgCl₂.6 H₂O (15.20 g, 0.075 mol) in DMF (100 mL), substitutedquinoline-3-carbonitrile (0.075 mol) was added. The mixture was stirred at 20 C for 18 hours and progress was monitored on TLC. On completion of the reaction, the mixture was poured in water (200 mL). The

precipitated solid was washed with water and then stirred in IN HCl (200 mL) for 20 minutes. After filtration and washing with water, the product was crystallized from toluene and hexane, obtaining the title compound, as a yellow solid.

2.1.5. General method of synthesis of compounds (16-18) (step-v)

A mixture of appropriate substituted 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbothioamide (13-15) (0.01mol) in absolute ethanol (10mL) containing chloroacetic acid (0.01mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.03mol) was refluxed for 6 hrs. The resulted product was poured onto ice-water (100 mL) and the formed precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.1.6. General method of synthesis of compounds (19a-19f), (20a-20f) and (21a-21f) (step-vi)

To a solution of compound (16-18) (0.02 mol), paraformaldehyde (0.025 mol) and suitable secondary amine (0.02 mol) in 15 ml of ethanol was added (1-2) drops of conc HCl. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6-10 on water bath. The progress of the reactions was monitored by TLC and on completion of the reaction; the content of the flask was reduced to half and left overnight at room temperature. The solid mass thus separated was collected by filtration, dried and recrystallized from ethanol/DMF.

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(dimethylamino)methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (19a)

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3353 (N-H), 2962 (C-H), 1685 (C = O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm: 2.33 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.81 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.64 (t, H, CH), 5.74 (s, 1H, CH), 7.50–7.55 (t, 1H, H-6, *J* = 7.0 Hz), 7.68–7.77 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 8.02–8.05 (d, 1H, H-8, *J* = 7.6 Hz), 8.16 (s, 1H, H-4). 10.23 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS *m/z* 321.07

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(diethylamino) methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (19b)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3349 (N-H), 2956 (C-H), 1682 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.07 (t, 6H, 2xCH₃), 2.46 (m, H, 2xCH₂), 3.52 (t, H, CH), 5.68 (s, 1H, CH), 7.49–7.54 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 7.53–7.74 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 8.01–8.03 (d, 1H, H-8, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 8.17 (s, 1H, H-4). 10.17 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 349.10

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**19c**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3351 (N-H), 2949 (C-H), 1691 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.49 (m, 6H, 3xCH₂), 2.53 (t, 2H, 2xCH₂), 3.08 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.64 (t, 1H, CH), 5.80 (s, 1H, CH), 7.46–7.51 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 7.66–7.75 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 7.98–8.00 (d, 1H, H-8, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 8.09 (s, 1H, H-4). 10.20 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 361.10

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**19d**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3410 (N-H), 2987 (C-H), 1700 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.31 (s, 3H, N-CH₃), 2.60 (t, 4H, 2 CH₂), 2.95 (t, 4H, 2 CH₂), 3.11 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.79 (t, 1H, CH), 5.72 (s, 1H, CH), 7.48–7.52 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 7.72–7.85 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 7.99–8.02 (d, 1H, H-8, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 8.21 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.39 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 376.11

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-(morpholin-4-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**19e**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3420 (N-H), 2998 (C-H), 1709 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.59 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.85 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.41 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 3.70 (t, H, CH), 5.84 (s, 1H, CH), 7.51–7.56 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 7.62–7.79 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 8.00–8.02 (d, 1H, H-8, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 8.19 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.45 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 363.08

2-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-5-(pyrrolidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**19f**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3365 (N-H), 2955 (C-H), 1712 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.76 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.44 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.82 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.67 (t, 1H, CH), 5.73 (s, 1H, CH), 7.48–7.53 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.2$

Hz), 7.53–7.66 (m, 2H, H-5 and H-7), 8.00–8.02 (d, 1H, H-8, $J = 6.9$ Hz), 8.13 (s, 1H, H-4). 10.29 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 347.09

2-(2-chloro-8-methylquinolin-3-yl)-5-(dimethylamino methyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20a**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3362 (N-H), 2959 (C-H), 1688 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.31 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.73 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.88 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.75 (t, 1H, CH), 5.78 (s, 1H, CH) 7.35–7.40 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 7.50–7.59 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.12 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.13 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 335.09

2-(2-chloro-8-methylquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(diethylamino methyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20b**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3345 (N-H), 2952 (C-H), 1679 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.05 (t, 6H, 2xCH₃), 2.41 (m, H, 2xCH₂), 2.69 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.80 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.49 (t, H, CH), 5.67 (s, 1H, CH), 7.37–7.42 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 7.49–7.55 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 9.48 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.03 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 363.12

2-(2-chloro-8-methyl-quinolin-3-yl)-5-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20c**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3348 (N-H), 2941 (C-H), 1689 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.49 (m, 6H, 3xCH₂), 2.53 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.71 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.08 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.64 (t, 1H, CH), 5.80 (s, 1H, CH), 7.34–7.40 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 7.52–7.61 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.13 (s, 1H, H-4), 9.95 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 375.12

2-(2-chloro-8-methyl-quinolin-3-yl)-5-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl) methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20d**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3412 (N-H), 2993 (C-H), 1712 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.29 (s, 3H, N-CH₃), 2.60 (m, 7H, 2xCH₂ & CH₃), 2.95 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 3.13 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.77 (t, 1H, CH), 5.78 (s, 1H, CH), 7.33–7.39 (t, 1H, H-6, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 7.55–7.69 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.19 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.54 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 390.13

2-(2-chloro-8-methylquinolin-3-yl)-5-(morpholin-4-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20e**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3425 (N-H), 2987 (C-H), 1719 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.44 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.75 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.89 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.48 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 3.73 (t, H, CH), 5.87 (s, 1H, CH), 7.38-7.42 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.2$ Hz), 7.52-7.65 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.14 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.69 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 377.10

2-(2-chloro-8-methylquinolin-3-yl)-5-(pyrrolidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**20f**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3361 (N-H), 2949 (C-H), 1675 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.68 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.19 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.37 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.76 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.59 (t, 1H, CH), 5.66 (s, 1H, CH), 7.29-7.35 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.6$ Hz), 7.51-7.63 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.05 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.30 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 361.10

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(dimethylamino) methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21a**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3367 (N-H), 2965 (C-H), 1694 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.25 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.80 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.74 (t, 1H, CH), 3.91 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 5.84 (s, 1H, CH), 7.36-7.41 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.2$ Hz), 7.56-7.68 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.10 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.16 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 351.08

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(diethylamino) methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21b**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3342 (N-H), 2949 (C-H), 1668 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.12 (t, 6H, 2xCH₃), 2.38 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.83 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.68 (t, H, CH), 3.79 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 5.76 (s, 1H, CH), 7.33-7.38 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.3$ Hz), 7.51-7.63 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.08 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.28 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 379.11

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21c**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3346 (N-H), 2943 (C-H), 1694 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.35 (m, 6H, 3xCH₂), 2.21 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 1.98 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.39 (t, 1H, CH), 3.68 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 5.77 (s, 1H, CH), 7.35-7.40 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.1$ Hz), 7.52-7.68 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.11 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.25 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 391.11

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21d**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3417 (N-H), 2997 (C-H), 1709 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.34 (s, 3H, N-CH₃), 2.64 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.89 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 3.17 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.70 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.82 (t, 1H, CH), 5.90 (s, 1H, CH), 7.40-7.45 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.2$ Hz), 7.65-7.79 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.11 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.52 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 406.12

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-(morpholin-4-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21e**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3430 (N-H), 2995 (C-H), 1725 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 2.39 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.52 (t, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.97 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.72 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.87 (t, H, CH), 5.92 (s, 1H, CH), 7.33-7.39 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.0$ Hz), 7.64-7.80 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.14 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.63 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 393.09

2-(2-chloro-8-methoxyquinolin-3-yl)-5-(pyrrolidin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**21f**)

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3375 (N-H), 2967 (C-H), 1698 (C = O);
 ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm: 1.53 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.13 (m, 4H, 2xCH₂), 2.78 (d, 2H, CH₂), 3.56 (t, 1H, CH), 3.88 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 5.84 (s, 1H, CH), 7.28-7.33 (t, 1H, H-6, $J=7.2$ Hz), 7.49-7.65 (m, 2H, H-5 and 7), 8.07 (s, 1H, H-4), 10.40 (bs, 1H, NH), ESI-MS m/z 377.10

2.2. Pharmacology

2.2.1. Anticonvulsant screening (13, 14)

All the animal handling procedures, sample administration and disposal were carried out according to the regulations of Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC), faculty of veterinary medicine, University of Sadat City, with approval number VUSC-005-1-21. Male albino mice weighing 25-30 g were used as investigational animal. Test compound were-

Table-1 Physical and chemical data of synthesized compounds

19a-f; 20a-f; 21a-f

Compd. No.	R	R'	Mol. Formula	Yield (%)	Mp. (°C)	Calculated (Found) %		
						C	H	N
19a	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	65	140–142	55.98 (56.12)	5.01 (5.02)	13.06 (13.10)
19b	H	N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ OS	59	161–162	58.36 (58.56)	5.76 (5.72)	12.01 (12.04)
19c	H		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ OS	62	159-163	59.74 (59.82)	5.57 (5.58)	11.61 (11.63)
19d	H		C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OS	56	152–153	56.27 (56.45)	5.28 (5.26)	15.44 (15.48)
19e	H		C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	72	144-147	56.12 (56.23)	4.99 (5.01)	11.55 (11.58)
19f	H		C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ OS	69	179–180	58.70 (58.89)	5.22 (5.23)	12.08 (12.10)
20a	CH ₃	N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ OS	63	149-151	57.22 (57.38)	5.40 (5.42)	12.51 (12.54)
20b	CH ₃	N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ OS	48	158-161	59.41 (59.45)	6.09 (6.11)	11.55 (11.57)
20c	CH ₃		C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ OS	60	172-173	60.71 (60.85)	5.90 (5.88)	11.18 (11.21)
20d	CH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ OS	58	146-148	57.36 (57.48)	5.62 (5.64)	14.87 (14.91)
20e	CH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	67	150-153	57.21 (57.48)	5.33 (5.34)	11.12 (11.15)
20f	CH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ OS	52	181-182	59.74 (59.86)	5.57 (5.56)	11.61 (11.63)

21a	OCH ₃	N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	66	128-130	54.62 (54.76)	5.16 (5.17)	11.94 (11.98)
21b	OCH ₃	N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	61	143-144	56.91 (57.01)	5.84 (5.83)	11.06 (11.09)
21c	OCH ₃		C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	55	190-192	58.23 (58.34)	5.66 (5.67)	10.72 (10.75)
21d	OCH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	63	155-156	55.02 (55.18)	5.39 (5.40)	14.26 (14.39)
21e	OCH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₃ S	78	163-164	54.89 (54.95)	5.12 (5.14)	10.67 (10.69)
21f	OCH ₃		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	70	199-201	57.21 (57.39)	5.33 (5.34)	11.12 (11.15)

suspended in PEG 200 for MES and *sc*PTZ evaluation. The animals were kept at an ambient temperature 22 ± 1 °C, in groups of six per cage under standard laboratory condition and permitted to free access to food and water.

2.2.1.1. Maximal Electroshock Seizure (MES) Test

Test compounds were administered as an intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection at dose level of 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg and the anticonvulsant activity was measured after 0.5 hr and 4 hrs intervals of administration. Maximal electroshock seizures were caused in mice by delivering 60Hz, 50mA electrical stimuli for 0.2 s via ear clip electrodes. Abolition of hind limb tonic extensor component of the seizure in half or more of the animals is expressed as protection.

2.2.1.2. Subcutaneous Pentylenetetrazole (*sc*PTZ) Seizure Test

The *sc*PTZ primarily pinpoints compounds that elevate seizure threshold. The *sc* PTZ test employs a dose of pentylenetetrazol (85 mg/kg). This yields clonic seizures lasting for a period of at least five seconds in 97 percent (CD₉₇) of animals tested.

Solutions of test compounds were administered intraperitoneally at dose level of 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg. At the estimated time of testing (0.5 hr and 4.0 hrs), the convulsant (PTZ) was administered subcutaneously and animals were observed over a 30 minute period. Absence of clonic seizure in half or more of the animals in the observed time period designated a compound's ability to eliminate the effect of pentylenetetrazol on seizure threshold.

2.3. Toxicity study

2.3.1. Rotarod test

The minimal motor damage was measured in mice by the rotarod test. The mice were skilled to stay on an accelerating rotarod of diameter 3.2 cm that rotates at 10 revolutions per minute (RPM). Neurotoxicity was designated by the inability of the animal to withstand equilibration on the rod for at least one minute in each of the three experiments. The dose at which 50% of the animals qualified to balance themselves and fell off the rotating rod was determined (15).

2.3.2. Ethanol Potentiation Test

Mice were subjected with the test compound and 1 h later with ethanol 2.5 g kg⁻¹*ip*. This dose of ethanol did not bring lateral position in the control animals. The

number of animals that were in the lateral position after getting ethanol in each group was determined (17).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chemistry

The synthetic pathway giving access to the titled compounds (**19a-f**, **20a-f** and **21a-f**) is illustrated in **Scheme 1**. The synthesis of N-aryl acetamide (**4-6**) involved a reaction among acetic acid, acetic anhydride and substituted anilines. In the subsequent step, 2-chloro-8-substitute dquinoline-3-carboxaldehyde (**7-9**) was synthesized by the treatment of compounds (**4-6**) with N, N- dimethylformamide (DMF) in phosphoryl chloride. Substituted quinoline-3-carbonitrile (**10-12**) was prepared when in a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium formate in formic acid; substituted quinoline-3-carbaldehyde was added.

Syntheses of substituted quinoline-2-carbothioamide (**13-15**) were afforded when substitutedquinoline-3-carbonitrile reacts with sodium hydrosulfide (NaSH) and magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) in DMF. Compounds (**16-18**) were prepared when 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbothioamide (**13-15**) in absolute ethanol containing chloroacetic acid and fused sodium acetate (0.03mol) was refluxed. Finally compounds (**19a-19f**), (**20a-20f**) and (**21a-21f**) were prepared when compounds (**16-18**) in paraformaldehyde react with suitable secondary amines. The physical parameters of the title compounds have been summarized in table 1.

All the synthesized compounds were well characterized by elemental analysis and spectroscopic data. The ¹H NMR spectra showed a methyl and methylene hydrogens at their respective chemical shift values. Various singlets, doublets, triplets, and multiplets were found in aromatic zones. A conspicuous broad singlet at δ values ranging from 10.69 to 9.48 ppm was assigned to N-H attached to the thiazolidinone ring.

3.2. Pharmacology

Anticonvulsant evaluation of compounds (**19a-f**, **20a-f** and **21a-f**) in mice utilizing MES and scPTZ models is summarized in Table 3 together with the neurotoxicity and ethanol potentiation data. To obtain information about undesired side effects, the highly and moderately active compounds were subjected to neurotoxicity (rotorod) and ethanol potentiation tests.

Preliminary evaluation of all the synthesized compounds was performed against two well-established seizure models, namely MES and scPTZ. All the compounds showed encouraging anticonvulsant activity. Compounds **19c**, **20b**, **20c**, **21b** and **21f** displayed maximum activity and comparable to the standard drug Phenytoin in MES test. Compounds **21b** and **21f** were found to have undergone rapid degradation, due to which these drugs displayed short duration of action. Compounds **19b**, **19f**, **20f** and **21c** showed moderate activity in comparison to standard drug phenytoin and carbamazepine in MES test. Except **21c**, all the moderately active agents are longer duration of action (Table 3).

Only those compounds which are moderately or maximally active were subjected to scPTZ test. The findings of the experiments showed compounds **20c**, **20d**, **21b** and **21f** showed potency at the dose of 100mg/kg which is comparable to standard drug carbamazepine. Compounds **20c** and **20d** degrade very fast and showed no activity at 4 hours of drug administration. The other chemo-shock active compounds, **21b** and **21f** showed low activity even after four hours of dosing indicated the ability of compounds to stay longer in animal's body (Table 3).

The neurotoxicity was evaluated using rotarod experiment. All those compounds were subjected to rotarod test which showed high to moderate activity against MES test. Only compound **21b** showed toxicity at a dose of 100mg/kg and ethanol potentiation test further confirmed the neurotoxicity of the compound (Table 3).

Table 2: *In silico* pharmacokinetic parameter of title compounds (18)

Comd. No.	LogP	^a BBB	^b BS (mg/l)	CYP-inhibition	^c HIA	^d PPB
19a	1.48	0.063	72.64	2D6-weak	96.31	60.07
19b	2.54	0.119	18.07	2D6-weak 3A4-substrate	96.46	75.76
19c	2.74	0.112	9.99	2D6-weak	96.55	82.25
19d	1.23	0.073	167.09	2D6- substrate 3A4- weak	96.56	43.85
19e	1.08	0.094	71.24	2D6-substrate	96.43	37.14
19f	2.17	0.106	19.52	2D6-weak	96.46	71.41
20a	1.94	0.053	29.04	2D6-weak 3A4-weak	96.38	68.06
20b	3.00	0.127	7.20	2D6-weak 3A4-substrate	96.54	80.59
20c	3.20	0.155	3.98	2D6-weak 3A4-weak	96.63	84.76
20d	1.69	0.059	28.34	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.47	47.46
20e	1.54	0.061	66.39	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.64	53.74
20f	2.63	0.099	7.78	2D6- weak 3A4-weak	96.54	77.48
21a	1.23	0.157	69.02	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.40	53.66
21b	2.30	0.140	17.05	2D6-substrate 3A4- substrate	96.47	69.79
21c	2.49	0.110	9.41	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.52	77.80
21d	0.99	0.132	156.79	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.55	42.15
21e	0.84	0.192	67.02	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.61	37.39
21f	1.93	0.143	18.43	2D6-substrate 3A4-weak	96.47	64.11

^aBlood brain barrier, ^bBuffer solubility, ^cHuman Intestinal Absorption, ^dPlasma Protein Binding.

Table 3: Anticonvulsant and neurotoxicity screen data of compounds (**19a-f**; **20a-f**; **21a-f**).

Compound Number	Intraperitoneal/subcutaneous injection in mice ^a						
	MES screening		scPTZ screening		Neurotoxicity screen		Ethanol
	0.5 h	4.0 h	0.5 h	4.0 h	0.5 h	4.0 h	Potentiation
19a	-	300	X	X	X	X	X
19b	100	100	300	-	-	-	-
19c	30	30	-	300	-	-	-
19d	-	300	-	-	-	-	-
19e	300	-	X	X	X	X	X
19f	100	100	300	-	-	-	-
20a	300	-	X	X	X	X	X
20b	30	30	300	-	-	-	-
20c	30	30	100	-	-	-	-
20d	300	300	100	-	X	-	-
20e	300	-	X	X	X	-	-
20f	100	100	-	-	-	+	+
21a	-	-	300	X	X	X	X
21b	30	100	100	300	100	-	+
21c	100	300	-	300	-	X	X
21d	-	-	X	X	X	X	X
21e	300	-	X	X	X	X	X
21f	30	100	100	300	-	-	-
Phenytoin	30	30	—	—	100	100	-
Carbamazepine	30	100	100	300	100	300	-

^aDoses of 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg of the compound were administered and the protection and neurotoxicity were evaluated after 0.5 and 4h. The data indicate the minimal dose required to cause protection or neurotoxicity in 50% or more of the animals. The dash (—) designates the absence of anticonvulsant activity or neurotoxicity. X— indicates not tested. ^bEthanol potentiation test: (+), half or more animals passed the test; (-), half or more animals failed the test. X— denotes not tested.

As far as in silico physicochemical and pharmacokinetic parameters were concerned as shown in table 2, majority the active compounds showed pharmacological activities in agreements with the afore-mentioned parameters. When we compared the lipophilicity of the newly synthesized compounds with the anticonvulsant activity, the results showed that majority of the active compounds were lipophilic. A direct correlation can be drawn from the lipophilicity and anticonvulsant activity except in case of the compound **21f**. Compound **21f** showed high anti-MES activity despite having low lipophilic profile. The blood brain barrier (BBB) values were more for the compounds showed high to moderate anti-MES activity except compound **20f**. The BBB values were also in agreement with the anti-MES activity. The other pharmacokinetic parameters, for example, buffer solubility (BS), human intestinal absorption (HIA), plasma protein binding (PPB) were also in agreement with the anticonvulsant activity.

4. Conclusions

In the present paper the authors reported the synthesis and antiepileptic screening of a series of quinoline-incorporated thiazolidin-4-ones. The synthesized compounds were characterized and subjected to maximal electroshock seizure (MES) and subcutaneous pentylenetetrazol (scPTZ)-induced seizure tests. Neurotoxicity was evaluated via rotarod and ethanol potentiation tests. Among the compounds tested, **19c**, **20b**, **20c**, **21b** and **21f** showed maximum protection against MES test model. In scPTZ test, compounds **20c**, **20d**, **21b** and **21f** showed maximum activity. In rotarod and ethanol potentiation tests only one compound that is **21b** showed neuromotor toxicity. More research is needed to validate the safety and efficacy of these compounds.

5. Acknowledgement:

The authors are thankful to Sadat University Egypt for providing the necessary facility to complete this research work.

6. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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